

HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AND WOMEN'S HEALTH

Kasimova V.S.

Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10748531>

Abstract. *Heathy lifestyle, which includes activities and habits that encourage the development of total physical, mental, and spiritual fitness, which reduces the risk of major illness. Women's health is a broad category that includes health issues that are unique to women, such as menstruation and pregnancy, as well as conditions that affect both men and women, but that may affect women differently, such as heart disease and diabetes. Healthy lifestyle and women's health were discussed in this article.*

Keywords: *health; lifestyle; women; major illness; spiritual fitness; balanced diet; energy; bodily activities; stress management.*

A wholesome life-style is one which helps to maintain and enhance people's health and well-being and can also assist overcome a lot of stress. Many governments and non-governmental corporations work in promotion healthful lifestyles. Healthy living is a lifelong effect. Being healthy includes healthy eating, bodily activities, weight management, and stress management. A healthful way of life consists of a balanced diet. This does not imply cutting out vital meals companies from your food regimen or limiting yourself on the quantity of energy per day.[1] A well-rounded diet entails eating most food organizations in each and every meal. Meats, dairy, fruits, and greens are all essential factors of a meal that will make certain your physique is healthy. Doing a healthful weight loss plan brings a life-style that can alternate your existence into being healthier and bodily fit. According to Jim Rohn, "Take care of your body. It's the solely place you have to live." Healthy life-style includes now not solely eating right but also questioning and saying right. We ought to stay away from foods that comprise high amounts of salt or sugar. These include preserving a healthy weight, getting normal exercise, following a wholesome diet, and no longer smoking. A healthful way of life can help you thrive as you go thru your life's journey. Making healthy preferences isn't always usually handy – it can be tough to find the time and electricity to exercise usually or put together wholesome meals. However, your efforts will pay off in many ways and for the relaxation of your life.[2]

Think you're leading a healthful lifestyle? Aside from now and again veering off the path, most of us suppose we do a truthful job of retaining our fitness with right (or at least OK) ingesting habits and physical exercise each time we manage to fit it in. But is that adequate to be viewed "healthy?" According to a recent study, very few adults simply meet the standards for a wholesome lifestyle. The study, published in the Archives of Internal Medicine, showed that solely 3% of American adults acquired a ideal score on what the authors say are the four simple criteria for wholesome living. Just 13.8% met three of the criteria; 34.2% met solely two criteria. Women scored slightly better than men.

When wondering about women's health, there is a lot to consider. Knowing the illnesses and stipulations that are amongst the pinnacle fitness dangers for women, such as coronary heart ailment and breast cancer, is important. But for many women, efficaciously managing different matters that affect daily health, such as premenstrual syndrome, start control, fertility, menopause and more, also is key to taking part in a shiny life. Women's health differs from that of men's

fitness in many special ways. Women's health is an instance of populace health, the place fitness is described through the World Health Organisation as "a state of complete physical, intellectual and social well-being and now not purely the absence of ailment or infirmity".[3] Often treated as really women's reproductive health, many companies argue for a broader definition pertaining to the overall fitness of women, higher expressed as "The health of women." These differences are further exacerbated in growing nations the place female whose fitness consists of each their risks and experiences are in addition disadvantaged.

While the charges of the main causes of death, cardiovascular disease, cancer, and lung disease are comparable in female and men, ladies have exceptional experiences. Lung cancer has overtaken all other kinds of cancer as the main reason of cancer related deaths in women, followed by means of breast cancer, colorectal, ovarian, and cervical cancers. While smoking is the principal reason of lung cancer, amongst nonsmoking women, the threat of growing cancer is three times higher than among nonsmoking men. Despite this, breast most cancers stays the most common cancer in female in developed countries, and is one of the primary continual ailments of women, while cervical most cancers stays one of the most common cancers in growing countries, related with human papilloma virus (HPV), a sexually transmitted infection. HPV vaccine, collectively with screening, presents the promise of controlling these diseases. Other necessary health problems for girls include cardiovascular disease, depression, dementia, osteoporosis, and anaemia. In 176 out of 178 nations for which data are available, there is a gender gap in want of women in lifestyles expectancy. In Western Europe, this has been the case at least as some distance again as 1750.[4] Gender stays an essential social determinant of fitness due to the fact that women's health is influenced now not simply with the aid of their biology but also by conditions such as poverty, employment, and household responsibilities. Women have long been disadvantaged in many respects such as social and monetary electricity which restricts their get admission to to the requirements of existence which include fitness care, and the larger the level of disadvantage, such as in creating countries, the greater adverse influence on health. Women's journey of health and sickness range from these of men due to special biological, social, and behavioural conditions. Biological differences fluctuate from phenotypes to cell biology and happen special risks for the improvement of sick health.

REFERENCES

1. Healthy Lifestyles. <https://www.ucsfhealth.org/education/healthy-lifestyles-healthy-outlook>.
2. Kathleen M. Zelman. 4 Steps to a Healthy Lifestyle. <https://www.webmd.com/diet/features/4-steps-healthy-lifestyle>.
3. Women's health. <https://www.mayoclinic.org/healthy-lifestyle/womens-health/basics/womens-health/hlv-20049411>.
4. Oraby, Doaa (February 2018). "Women living with HIV in the Middle East and north Africa". The Lancet.
5. https://scholar.google.ru/citations?hl=ru&view_op=list_works&gmla=AH70aAXiFVJ6SwF_NpIKngioAvfy1mlcHAZJrCfXLcDQjPti1kn6WKNnhGH391UzKgzcOVNBy-zsvMR5RwQR0DNs6fpfqCCjjmR0TVEb8GIHY7y8ztIx1jeEs&user=eEdSCvYAAAAJ